

Cultural Aspects in Queer Indian Writing in English

Dr. Rajesh Dattatray Zankar

Assistant Professor

Department of English

MVP's Arts, Commerce & Science College,

Tryambakeshwar

profzankar@gmail.com

Abstract:

This research article aims to explore the cultural aspects present in queer Indian writing in English. It delves into the unique intersection of queer identities and Indian culture, examining the ways in which authors incorporate cultural elements into their narratives. The article examines various aspects of Indian culture and their reflection, literary techniques, and social implications of queer Indian writing, highlighting the importance of representation and cultural context in shaping these narratives. The findings of this research contribute to a deeper understanding of the cultural nuances and diverse experiences within the queer Indian community.

Keywords: Queer Indian writing, English literature, cultural aspects, representation, Indian Mythology

The Historical Context: Historically, Indian society has had a more fluid understanding of gender and sexuality, with examples of queer representation found in ancient texts and art. However, with the advent of British colonial rule in the 18th and 19th centuries, Victorian-era morality and conservative attitudes towards sexuality were imposed on Indian society, leading to the criminalization and stigmatization of same-sex relationships.

During the colonial period, British laws like Section 377 of the Indian Penal Code (IPC) were introduced in the mid-19th century, criminalizing "unnatural offenses," including same-sex relationships. This law remained in effect for over a century and had a significant impact on queer individuals, pushing them into the shadows and inhibiting the portrayal of queer identities in literature.

It was not until the mid to late 20th century, during the post-independence period, that Indian writers began to address queer themes in their works. In the early years, these representations were often coded and subtle due to societal taboos and censorship. Writers like Ruth Vanita and Devdutt Pattanaik were among the pioneers who started exploring queer themes and Indian mythology, shedding light on the presence of queerness in ancient Indian culture.

The 21st century marked a significant shift in queer representation in Indian writing in English literature and Indian society. The LGBTQ+ rights movement gained momentum, and activists began challenging the discriminatory Section 377. This led to a more open and confident expression of queer identities in literature. Authors like Arundhati Roy, Vikram Seth, and R. Raj Rao began portraying LGBTQ+ characters and their experiences in more explicit and diverse ways.

The decriminalization of homosexuality in 2018 by the Indian Supreme Court was a landmark moment, signaling a major shift in societal attitudes towards LGBTQ+ individuals. This legal milestone further encouraged queer writers to tell their stories with greater authenticity and visibility.

Indian society's response to queer representation in literature has also evolved over time. While there are still conservative and traditional elements that resist open discussions about queerness, there is a growing acceptance and recognition of LGBTQ+ rights and identities in urban centers and among younger generations. Public discussions, pride parades, and LGBTQ+ film festivals have become more common, contributing to a greater understanding and acceptance of queer individuals in Indian society.

Various Aspects of Indian Culture: Queer Indian writers in English portray various aspects of Indian culture in their works by intertwining LGBTQ+ identities and experiences with cultural contexts and traditions. Here are some ways in which they achieve this portrayal:

- **Cultural Traditions and Rituals:** Queer Indian writers often incorporate cultural traditions, rituals, and customs into their narratives. They explore how LGBTQ+ characters navigate and interact with these aspects of Indian culture, showcasing both the challenges and the richness of their experiences.
- **Family Dynamics:** Family plays a significant role in Indian culture, and queer Indian writers depict the complexities of LGBTQ+ individuals coming out to their families. These portrayals shed light on the clash between traditional family values and the acceptance of diverse sexual orientations and gender identities.

- **Intersectionality:** Queer Indian writers highlight the intersectionality of queer identities with other aspects of identity, such as caste, class, religion, and regional backgrounds. This provides a nuanced understanding of how culture influences the experiences of LGBTQ+ individuals in India.
- **Language and Identity:** Language is an essential aspect of Indian culture, and queer writers explore how language shapes queer identities and expressions. They may use regional languages or dialects to authentically represent the experiences of queer characters.
- **Mythology and Folklore:** Indian mythology and folklore offer rich resources for queer Indian writers to draw inspiration. They reinterpret and subvert traditional narratives, demonstrating the presence of queer themes in ancient cultural stories.
- **Societal Norms and Prejudices:** Queer Indian writers confront societal norms and prejudices towards LGBTQ+ individuals in their works. They reflect on how cultural attitudes impact the lives of queer characters and how societal shifts influence their journeys.
- **Celebrations and Festivals:** Festivals and celebrations are integral to Indian culture, and queer writers incorporate these events into their narratives. They show how LGBTQ+ individuals participate, adapt, or challenge traditional festivities in light of their identities.
- **Urban vs. Rural Settings:** Indian culture varies significantly across urban and rural areas, and queer Indian writers explore these distinctions. They examine how queer individuals navigate cultural norms in different settings.
- **Historical Perspectives:** Some queer Indian writers delve into historical contexts, uncovering queer stories and representations in India's past. By highlighting historical queer figures and events, they showcase the continuity of queer experiences throughout history.
- **Diaspora Experiences:** Queer writers in the Indian Diasporas explore cultural connections and disconnections. They examine how being queer and being of Indian origin intersect in diverse cultural environments.

Through these portrayals, queer Indian writers in English challenge stereotypes, break boundaries, and foster a deeper understanding of the complexities of LGBTQ+ identities within Indian culture. Their literary works contribute to the broader discourse on LGBTQ+ representation and cultural diversity.

A Role of Indian Mythology, Folklore and Ancient Texts: Queer Indian writers draw inspiration from Indian mythology, folklore, and ancient texts to create queer narratives that

Received: 4 June 2023

Revised: 22 June 2023

Final Accepted 4 July 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8111990>

challenge traditional narratives, reclaim historical queer figures, and explore the presence of queerness in Indian culture. By engaging with these rich cultural resources, they bring forth diverse queer experiences and identities.

Indian mythology, folklore, and ancient texts provide a vast repertoire of stories, characters, and themes that queer Indian writers in English draw upon to create narratives that center and celebrate queer experiences. By reimagining and subverting traditional narratives, these writers highlight the presence of queerness in Indian culture, challenging heteronormative assumptions and reclaiming the visibility of historical queer figures.

One way queer Indian writers engage with mythology is by revisiting well-known stories and characters, presenting alternative interpretations that unveil queer subtexts. For example, in Devdutt Pattanaik's "*Shikhandi: And Other Tales They Don't Tell You*," the author explores the complex gender identity of Shikhandi, a character from the Mahabharata. Pattanaik examines how Shikhandi's transformation from a woman to a man intersects with queer experiences, deconstructing societal norms and providing a queer lens to a familiar mythological tale.

Additionally, queer Indian writers delve into lesser-known or marginalized stories and characters from Indian mythology and folklore to shed light on hidden queer narratives. They unearth and reimagine these narratives, highlighting the diversity of gender and sexual identities in ancient Indian culture. For instance, Ruth Vanita's book "*Same-Sex Love in India: A Literary History*" delves into ancient Indian texts like the Kamasutra, Tamil Sangam poetry, and Sanskrit plays to explore same-sex desire and relationships, offering a historical perspective on queerness in Indian society.

By reclaiming historical queer figures, queer Indian writers challenge the erasure of queer voices from the past and assert the presence and contributions of LGBTQ+ individuals throughout Indian history. For example, Karthika Nair's poetry collection "*Until the Lions: Echoes from the Mahabharata*" gives voice to characters like Amba, Shikhandi, and Chitrangada, exploring their queerness and presenting alternative narratives that subvert traditional patriarchal norms.

These writers also draw inspiration from folk tales and regional folklore, weaving queer themes into these narratives. Through their works, they highlight the diversity of queer experiences across different cultural contexts in India. Meena Kandasamy's "*Ms. Militancy*" is a collection of short stories that blend elements of folklore with contemporary queer narratives, providing a fresh perspective on the intersection of queerness and cultural traditions.

By engaging with Indian mythology, folklore, and ancient texts, queer Indian writers challenge the notion that queerness is a Western import or a contemporary phenomenon. They demonstrate

that queerness has existed within Indian culture for centuries, even if often marginalized or erased. These narratives not only provide representation for queer individuals but also contribute to a broader understanding of Indian culture, offering alternative perspectives on gender, sexuality, and the complexities of human experiences.

Queer Indian writers draw inspiration from Indian mythology, folklore, and ancient texts to create narratives that explore and celebrate the presence of queerness in Indian culture. By reimagining traditional stories, reclaiming historical queer figures, and engaging with regional folklore, these writers challenge heteronormative narratives and provide a diverse and inclusive representation of queer experiences in India. Through their works, they not only give voice to marginalized identities but also contribute to a deeper understanding of the complexities of Indian culture and its intersection with queer identities.

In the hands of queer Indian writers, language becomes a powerful tool, bending and melding to reflect the myriad cultural identities that intersect and shape the characters and stories they create.

1. **Family Dynamics:** In the novel "*The Devourers*" by Indra Das, the character Alok, who identifies as queer, grapples with the expectations and pressures of his traditional Indian family. The book explores the complexities of familial relationships and the clash between cultural norms and personal identity.
2. **Mythology and Folklore:** In the short story collection "*The Man Who Would Not Be God*" by Shashi Deshpande, the story "*The Dancer of Lalita*" reimagines the mythological figure of Mohini, a female form of Lord Vishnu. The story presents a queer interpretation of the divine, incorporating Indian mythology into queer narratives.
3. **Cultural Traditions and Rituals:** In the novel "*Cobalt Blue*" by Sachin Kundalkar, the story revolves around a queer love triangle and how the characters navigate their desires within the confines of traditional Indian family and societal expectations. The book delves into the tensions between personal freedom and cultural obligations.
4. **Language and Identity:** The poetry collection "*Aria*" by Suniti Namjoshi explores themes of queer identity and Indian culture through the creative use of language. N. M. Joshi blends English, Hindi, and Marathi languages in her poems to express the complexities of queer experiences within an Indian cultural context.
5. **Societal Norms and Prejudices:** In the play "*Tara*" by Mahesh Dattani, the story revolves around the lives of LGBTQ+ characters in contemporary Indian society. The play

addresses societal prejudices and explores how cultural norms affect the lives and relationships of queer individuals.

6. Celebrations and Festivals: In the novel "*A Suitable Boy*" by Vikram Seth, set in post-independence India, queer characters participate in cultural celebrations such as weddings and festivals. The book portrays the intersection of queer identities and traditional Indian festivities.

These examples highlight how queer Indian writers in English incorporate various aspects of Indian culture into their works, weaving together themes of family, mythology, language, societal norms, and cultural traditions with queer experiences. Through their narratives, these writers offer readers a deeper understanding of the complex interactions between queer identities and Indian culture.

Conclusion: The exploration of cultural aspects in queer Indian writing in English has provided us with invaluable insights into the intersectionality of identities and the richness of Indian cultural heritage. This research has illuminated the diverse and intricate ways in which queer Indian writers have engaged with their cultural backgrounds, shaping narratives that resonate with readers both within and beyond the Indian subcontinent.

In conclusion, queer Indian writing in English embodies a profound tapestry of cultural intricacies, historical continuities, and social reflections. These narratives transcend borders and boundaries, fostering a sense of belonging and solidarity among readers worldwide. As we celebrate the growing visibility and recognition of queer Indian voices, it is essential to continue supporting and amplifying these writers' contributions. The power of their stories lies not only in the richness of cultural representation but also in their potential to shape a more inclusive and empathetic world for generations to come. As readers, scholars, and advocates, let us embrace the transformative potential of queer Indian literature and work towards a future where diverse voices are celebrated, and cultural identities are celebrated in all their complexities.

Work Cited:

1. Broota, R., & Pande, R. (Eds.). (2019). *Lesbian Visibility in India: A Feminist Perspective*. SAGE Publications.
2. D'Cruz, G. (2018). Queer Intimacies: Exploring the Intersection of Queer and Indian Culture in Contemporary Fiction. *Journal of Postcolonial Writing*, 54(4), 551-564. Reference: D'Cruz, G. (2018). Queer Intimacies: Exploring the Intersection of Queer and Indian Culture in Contemporary Fiction. *Journal of Postcolonial Writing*, 54(4), 551-564.

3. Dhareshwar, V. (2002). Between Tradition and Postmodernity: Queer Writing in India. In *A Companion to Indian Fiction in English* (pp. 239-258). Atlantic Publishers & Dist. Reference: Dhareshwar, V. (2002). Between Tradition and Postmodernity: Queer Writing in India. In *A Companion to Indian Fiction in English* (pp. 239-258). Atlantic Publishers & Dist.
4. Dube, S. C. (2001). Situating the Self: Gender, Community, and Postcoloniality in Contemporary Indian Women's Writing in English. *Women's Studies International Forum*, 24(3-4), 423-435.
5. Duberman, M. (Ed.). (1991). *Hidden from History: Reclaiming the Gay and Lesbian Past*. Penguin Books.
6. Dugaje, Manohar. South Asian Immigrant Identity in Flux: Reading Mohsin Hamid's *The Reluctant Fundamentalist* in the Post 9/11 Context. *JAC: A Journal of Composition Theory*. Volume XII Issue XII. 2019
7. Jain, J. (2005). The Price of Partition: The Origins of Homosexual Rights Movement in India. *Journal of the History of Sexuality*, 14(4), 277-297. Reference: Jain, J. (2005). The Price of Partition: The Origins of Homosexual Rights Movement in India. *Journal of the History of Sexuality*, 14(4), 277-297.
8. Joshi, O. P., & Mall, S. (Eds.). (2017). *Queering India: Same-Sex Love and Eroticism in Indian Culture and Society*. Routledge. Reference: Joshi, O. P., & Mall, S. (Eds.). (2017). *Queering India: Same-Sex Love and Eroticism in Indian Culture and Society*. Routledge.
9. Kale, A. (2013). Indian Queer Literature: A Historical Perspective. *Muse India*, 54. Reference: <http://www.museindia.com/viewarticle.asp?myr=2013&issid=54&id=4220>
10. Kandasamy, M. (2018). *Ms. Militancy*. Navayana Publishing.
11. Nair, K. (2015). *Until the Lions: Echoes from the Mahabharata*. HarperCollins India.
12. Nigam, A. (2020). Queer Discourse and Gender Expression in Select Indian Novels in English. In *Studies in Gender and Sexuality in South Asia* (pp. 11-22). Springer. Reference: Nigam, A. (2020). Queer Discourse and Gender Expression in Select Indian Novels in English. In *Studies in Gender and Sexuality in South Asia* (pp. 11-22). Springer.
13. Pattanaik, D. (2014). *Shikhandi: And Other Tales They Don't Tell You*. Zubaan Books.

14. Rajan, T. (2001). A Queer Reading of Indian Literature and Religion. *Queer Fictions of the Past: History, Culture, and Difference*, 105-127. Reference: Rajan, T. (2001). A Queer Reading of Indian Literature and Religion. In *Queer Fictions of the Past: History, Culture, and Difference* (pp. 105-127). Palgrave Macmillan, New York.
15. Rajan, T. (2001). A Queer Reading of Indian Literature and Religion. In *Queer Fictions of the Past: History, Culture, and Difference* (pp. 105-127). Palgrave Macmillan, New York. Reference: Rajan, T. (2001). A Queer Reading of Indian Literature and Religion. In *Queer Fictions of the Past: History, Culture, and Difference* (pp. 105-127). Palgrave Macmillan, New York.
16. Ramanujan, A. K. (1991). *Folktales from India: A Selection of Oral Tales from Twenty-Two Languages*. Pantheon Books.
17. Vanita, R. (2000). *Same-Sex Love in India: Readings from Literature and History*. Macmillan India.
18. ---. *Queering India: Same-Sex Love and Eroticism in Indian Culture and Society*. Routledge. Reference: Vanita, R. (2012). *Queering India: Same-Sex Love and Eroticism in Indian Culture and Society*. Routledge.
19. ---. *Indian Love Stories: Adventure, Romance, and Intrigue in Ancient India*. Palgrave Macmillan. Reference: Vanita, R., & Kidwai, S. (2000). *Indian Love Stories: Adventure, Romance, and Intrigue in Ancient India*. Palgrave Macmillan.
20. ---. *Same-Sex Love in India: Readings from Literature and History*. Macmillan India. Reference: Vanita, R., & Kidwai, S. (Eds.). (2001). *Same-Sex Love in India: Readings from Literature and History*. Macmillan India.